

Human Resource Management (HRM): A Research Study Analysis in the Academe Industry

CHRISTOPHER M. LEE
Technological Institute of the Philippines - Manila
christopherlee9888@gmail.com

June, 2022

ABSTRACT

The construction of the research article is my understanding and my research investigation requirement in the subject Human Resource Management (HRM). Since March 2020, the Covid-19 strikes the Philippines that cause economic stress and adversities which the education sector have to fully addressed and planned several measureable processes to resolve problems about these global pandemic. One of these challenges is the use of the HR Analytics and Metrics, by improving company performance on reducing workforce costs, improving the quality of recruitment, improving talent management and employee engagement, and by generally improving the business productivity itself. Diliman College - Quezon City always use the concept of HR Analytics and Metrics to ensure predictive management decisions always analyzes, contributes, and fulfills the human resource demands of the organization.

Keywords: *Human Resource Management (HRM), Covid-19, education sector, HR Analytics and Metrics, Diliman College - Quezon City*

INTRODUCTION

An HR review analysis and several HR educational mapping projects were made so far to surpassed the challenges of today. That is why school administrators, academic heads, and the subject teachers themselves are acquiring different strategies on how recruitment and manpower requirements improve and appealing to them. It has been said that before the companies settle to hire new employees, the firm should be engage and maintain a formal recruiting processes that involves the three HR components: Planning, Recruitment, and Employee Selection. HR Planning takes place with the number of potential employees they are hiring. The skills, competencies and other employee credentials must be achievable according to the manpower expectations.

On the other hand, the Recruitment should be consistent in terms of their job posting, campus recruitment, and referrals. This will measure hiring assessments, employment verifications, and competency objectives. Lastly, the Employee Selection

process contributes employment evaluations, feedbacks, which are generated by the applicant overall qualifications. This will simply assess, checks, and evaluates every skilled candidates on a given job position.

The research study article includes the existing HR programs and practices in the academe industry are said to be guided by its following areas of concentration: (a.) Recruitment – it focuses on how to calculate the hiring costs and job evaluations and the selection process; (b.) HR Training Metrics – quantifiable and measurable by using the ROI calculations; and (c.) Employee Productivity Metrics – refers to the job productivity performance results of an employee in the private education sector.

Throughout the research study about human resource management (HRM) in the academic sector, both quantitative and qualitative, and descriptive interpretations are used to complete the research project. And to better support the entire research problem, survey instruments were dependent on the following questions:

- 1.) What HR Tool is being used by the company to measure the:
 - a.) Recruitment Metrics for Applicants
 - b.) Training HR Metrics for Employees
 - c.) Productivity HR Metrics for Employees

- 2.) Please give one computation on each of the given HR Metrics?
(Recruitment, Training, and Productivity)

- 3.) From 1-3, please rate the:
For A: (3 = Satisfied; 2 = Not Satisfied; 3 = No Comment)
For B: (3 = Always; 2 = Not Always; 1 = No Comment)
For C: (3 = Agree; 2 = Disagree; 1 = No Comment)

A. Effectiveness
B. Usefulness
C. Accuracy

- 4.) Any Comment or Suggestions?

Image 1. Survey Instrument used in conducting a research study

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Hiring is the process of employing an individual. According to Doyle (2017), companies undergo a sequential process before employing an applicant for a job position that includes planning, recruitment and employee selection. Nowadays, advancement of technology and modernized recruitment is evident and influential in making a difference in positioning applicants in different organizations. Meanwhile, innovation of technology and modernized employment is currently evident and influential in making a difference in matching job applicants in different organizations (Kishu, 2016) **Unilab Foundation (2016)**. Equal work opportunities for all should be given regardless of their productivity or ability to produce **Joly & Venturiello (2012)**. HR Analytics today is targeting critical workforce metric that link workforce strategy to business results that finally provides HR a seat at the table and the integrity to make business and workforce strategy decisions by identifying cost savings opportunities, improving the retention of key talent and increasing workforce productivity and efficiency. **Higgins, J., Cooperstein, G. and Peterson, M. (2011)**

Larger organizations and rapidly growing companies will often hire a full-time, on-staff recruiter or recruiting team. Depending on the positions they are trying to fill, internal recruiters will often rely on and manage the talent acquisition approaches referenced above. Depending on the size of the company, a recruiting team will consist of HR professionals focused on talent sourcing – generating candidate leads through sourcing channels such as job boards, social media, and offline networking – and others focused on the actual recruiting of the candidates – “selling” them on the benefits of joining the organization. In smaller organizations, the internal recruiter will often perform both the sourcing & recruiting functions, often while performing other HR generalist functions. **Brenchley, C. (2019)**

Meanwhile, a research study article entitled: “The Future of Work: A Literature Review, 2018”, the ILO focused on five dimensions of the future of work wherein current changes will impact the world of work: (1) the future of jobs; (2) quality of jobs; (3) wage and income inequality; (4) social protection systems; and (5) social dialogue and industrial relations. The future of jobs refers to job creation, job destruction or the future composition of the labor force. In contrast, the future of job quality touches on issues like future working conditions or the sustainability of social protection system **(Balliester and Elsheikhi 2018)**.

Human Resource Metrics

Momin & Mishra (2015) highlight how the strategic workforce planning provides a multi-dimensional approach towards building human capital. HR analytics help to identify the skills and create the leaders of tomorrow. Thus, with the help of HR analytics a strategic workforce plan will reduce attrition rate, mitigate risks and build a value added training culture for the organization.

HR metrics examples in recruitment: Vulpen, E.V. (2022)

1.) Time to hire (time in days)

An important metric for recruitment is the 'time to hire'. This measures the number of days between a candidate applying for a job, and them accepting a job offer. Time to hire gives insights into recruiting efficiency and candidate experience. Recruitment efficiency measures the speed at which HR processes a candidate – assessment, interview, and role acceptance. If your organization has a long time to hire, it reflects that your processes are inefficient. Having a long time to hire, reflects on candidate experience. Candidates may drop out of the recruitment process if it is long. Wouldn't you rather wait two weeks than two months to start a new job? The best candidates are in demand and do not need to wait. Time to hire, should not be confused with time to fill. This metric typically measures the days between the approval of a job requisition and the candidate accepting the job offer. This definition is in line with the Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM) and ISO 30414.

2.) Cost per hire (total cost of hiring/the number of new hires)

Like the time to hire, the 'cost per hire (CPH)' metric shows how much it costs the company to hire new employees. This also serves as an indicator of the efficiency of the recruitment process. Cost per hire can be time-consuming to work out. There used to be a huge variation in how companies calculated this metric until The Society of Human Resource Management and the American National Standards Institute agreed on a standard formula. CPH can be calculated by adding together internal recruiting costs, and external recruiting costs, divided by total number of hires. The costs and number of hires will both reflect a selected measurement period – such as monthly, or annually.

3.) Early turnover (percentage of recruits leaving in the first year)

This is arguably the most important metric to determine hiring success in a company. This early leaver metric indicates whether there is a mismatch between the person and the company or between the person and his/her position. Early turnover is also very expensive. It usually takes 6 to 12 months before employees have fully learned the ropes and reach their 'Optimum Productivity Level'. According to a 2018 Glassdoor survey, the average cost of employee turnover in the UK is £11,000 per person.

4.) Time since last promotion (avg time in months since last internal promotion)

This rather straightforward metric is useful in explaining why your high potentials leave.

5.) Revenue per employee (revenue/total number of employees)

This metric shows the efficiency of the organization as a whole. The 'revenue per employee' metric is an indicator of the quality of hired employees. Check this Business Insider article to view how the top 12 tech companies in the world score on this metric.

6.) Performance and potential (the 9-box grid)

The 9-box grid appears when measuring and mapping both an individual's performance and potential in three levels. This model shows which employees are underperformers, valued specialists, emerging potentials, or top talents. This metric is great for differentiating between, for example, wanted and unwanted turnover. In another article, we wrote about the qualitative and quantitative ways to measure employee performance. Metrics include Net Promoter Score, management by objectives, number of errors, 360-degree feedback, forced ranking, etc.

7.) Billable hours per employee

This is the most concrete example of a performance measure, and it is especially relevant in professional service firms (e.g. law and consultancy firms). Relating this kind of performance to employee engagement or other input metrics makes for an interesting analysis. Benchmarking this metric between different departments and managers/partners can also provide valuable insights. This metric also relates to employee utilization rate, which refers to the amount of working time employee is spending on billable tasks.

8.) Engagement rating

An engaged workforce is a productive workforce. Engagement might be the most important 'soft' HR outcome. People who like their job and who are proud of their company are generally more engaged, even if the work environment is challenging and pressure can be high. Engaged employees perform better and are more likely to perceive challenges as positive and interesting. Additionally, team engagement is an important metric for a team manager's success.

9.) Cost of HR per employee

This metric shows the cost efficiency of HR expressed in dollars.

10.) Ratio of HR professionals to employees

HR to employee ratio is another measure that shows HR's cost efficiency. An organization with fully developed analytical capabilities should be able to have a smaller number of HR professionals do more.

11.) Ratio of HR business partners per employee

A similar metric to the previous one. Again, a set of highly developed analytics capabilities will enable HR to measure and predict the impact of HR policies. This will enable HR to be more efficient and reduce the number of business partners.

12.) Turnover (number of leavers/total population in the organization)

This metric shows how many workers leave the company in a given year. When combined with, for instance, a performance metric, the 'turnover' metric can track the difference in attrition in high and low performers. Preferably you would like to see low performers leave and high performers stay. This metric also provides HR business partners with a great amount of information about the departments and functions in which employees feel at home, and where in the organization they do not want to work. Turnover is very useful data to know when shaping recruitment strategies. Additionally, attrition could be a key metric in measuring a manager's success.

13.) Effectiveness of HR software

This is a more complex metric. Effectiveness of, for instance, learning and development software are measured in the number of active users, average time on the platform, session length, total time on platform per user per month, screen flow, and software retention. These metrics enable HR to determine what works for the employees and what does not.

14.) Absenteeism (absence percentage)

Like turnover, absenteeism is also a strong indicator of dissatisfaction and a predictor of turnover. Absenteeism rate can give information to prevent this kind of leave, as long-term absence can be very costly. Again, differences between individual managers and departments are very interesting indicators of (potential) problems and bottlenecks.

Human Resource Metrics and Business Impact

Ulrich's study (1997) shows the impact of HR on business results, by showing how HR practices relate to a business' balance scorecard through productivity, people and process indicators; and by showing how to audit HR practices, professionals, and departments. He also argues that one of the most common weaknesses of HR professionals is fear of quantitative, measurable results and such fears may come from a lack of knowledge or experience with empirical assessments of HR work. Several studies look into the relationship between technological progress and labor market outcomes. For instance, **Aghion and Howitt (1994)** cite two ways in which technological progress affect employment opportunities: (1) as new technologies serve as a substitute for labor, workers are forced to reallocate their labor supply –this is referred to as the destruction effect; (2) higher productivity will encourage more industries, expanding employment opportunities for workers –this is referred to as the capitalization effect. **Golden and Katz (2009)** explain that workers are able to survive such changes in the labor market due to their ability to adapt and retrain themselves through education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research paper is both a quantitative and qualitative study about the HR Metrics made by Diliman College - Quezon City. These are facilitated through the use of available resources within the organization like electronic proposals and survey instrument reports. The following tools given are being used in conducting a research study, and some were done by interviewing few HR personnel of the said organization. Throughout the said research study, the information are considered comprehensive based on the gathering of information.

Part 1. Human Resource Management (HRM) Metric: Recruitment

Recruitment in Diliman College - Quezon City whether teaching or non-teaching job positions involves several steps on how HR are considered for their standard human resource mechanisms and selection processes in the company. For many years now, the academic institutions relied on its single recruitment and advertisement method: that is to advertise all teaching and non-teaching vacancies in a newspaper, online job portals like Indeed.com.ph and Jobstreet.com.ph, and to their website. The basic job requirements were to place these publications lasted for 2-3 weeks. This will always be dependent on the number of job vacancies and employment substitutions within them. My employment as a SHS Faculty from the said employer took me 2 weeks to complete the entire application. Of course, there were several HR processes to comply, and there are some employment requirements to be submitted.

Image 2. Sample job advertisement of Diliman College - Quezon City

The job application package included the following information:

- An application form
- A company brochure about the school information
- And a formal application letter that details the entire application process

With regards towards the standard recruitment and selection process, according to Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines, the following template are issued upon its preparation for the Covid-19 resiliency. It serve as a profiling insertion towards a resolution by the recruitment and selection guidelines of most schools, colleges, and universities in the time of Covid-19 S.Y. 2020-2021:

RPMS Tool for Teacher I-III (Proficient Teachers) in the time of COVID-19 S.Y. 2020-2021			
	POSITION AND COMPETENCY PROFILE	PCP No. _____	Revision Code: 00
Position Title	Teacher I – III	Salary Grade	
Parenthetical Title			
Office Unit		Effectivity Date	
Reports to	Principal/School Heads	Page/s	
Position Supervised			
JOB			
QUALIFICATION STANDARDS			
A. CSC Prescribed Qualifications (For Senior High School Teachers, please refer to: DO 3, s. 2016; DO 27, s. 2016; and DO 51, s. 2017)			
Position Title	Teacher I	Teacher II	Teacher III
Education	For Elementary School – Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) or Bachelor's degree plus 18 professional units in Education, or Bachelor in Secondary Education, or its equivalent		
	For Secondary School – Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) or Bachelor's degree plus 18 professional units in Education with appropriate major or Bachelor in Secondary Education, or its equivalent		
Experience	None required	1 year relevant experience	2 years relevant experience
Eligibility	RA 1080	RA 1080	RA 1080
Trainings	None required	None required	None required
B. Preferred Qualifications			
Education	BSE/BSEEd/College Graduate with Education units (18-21), at least 18 MA units		
Experience	Teaching experience/s		
Eligibility	PBET/LET/BLEPT Passer		
Trainings	In-service training		

Image 3. DepEd RPMS Tool for Teacher 1-3

DUTIES AND RESPONSIBILITIES:
1. Applies mastery of content knowledge and its application across learning areas
2. Facilitates learning using appropriate and innovative teaching strategies and classroom management practices
3. Manages an environment conducive to learning
4. Addresses learner diversity
5. Implements and supervises curricular and co-curricular programs to support learning
6. Monitors and evaluates learner progress and undertakes activities to improve learner performance
7. Maintains updated records of learners' progress
8. Counsels and guides learners
9. Works with relevant stakeholders, both internal and external, to promote learning and improve school performance
10. Undertakes activities towards personal and professional growth
11. Does related work

Image 3 (continuation). DepEd RPMS Tool for Teacher 1-3

Recruitment and Selection Process:

The recruitment and selection processes for both teaching and non-teaching positions were not strict and rigid not to be compared with supervisory and managerial positions. Job advertisements were posted on both newspaper (classified ad section), online job portals, and from their company website 30 days in advance before the selection, onboarding and the start of the school year. Job titles and job descriptions are specifically arranged based on the manpower requirements. Applicants must apply online or face-to-face according to their credentials and qualifications. Potential applicant who passed the preliminary selection were being called for the next step of the application. For teaching positions, a teaching demonstration is a requirement to measure the mastery of teaching skills of the applicant. For non-teaching positions, initial and panel interviews must comply and pass by the candidate.

HR Metric used by the Recruitment:

As I got the Survey Instrument and gathered the research results output, it is finally revealed that the academic institution uses an HR metric known as the "Time to Fill" and "Time to Hire". These HR metric were used to facilitate the overall recruitment processes on both teaching and non-teaching positions of the organization. As the institution execute the HR metric, the HR progression on hiring teaching and non-teaching positions will not take longer than unusual. The management decided to considered applicants based on their performance on both oral and written

assessments.

Time to Fill Human Resource Management (HRM) Metric: Lancu, S. (2022)

Time to fill is one of the most crucial recruiting metrics for any organization, irrespective of industry, size of organization, and role. What exactly does time to fill refer to? How does it differ from time to hire, and can you calculate time to fill? And what are some tactics to reduce time to fill at your organization?

Imagine working for a marketing company and having a vacancy for a marketing manager in one of your regions. The knock-on effect of not having a marketing manager in place is that other managers would have to take on extra responsibility – leading to increased stress and frustration. Or if you work in the medical field, and you have a vacancy for a doctor. This would result in other doctors having to work overtime or a frustrated patient base due to a lack of service. Being able to measure the time to fill a vacancy is a crucial HR metric, which also impacts your business bottom line.

What is Time to Fill?

Time to Fill refers to the number of calendar days it takes to find and hire a new candidate is typically measured by the number of days between approving a job requisition and the candidate accepting your offer.

Some companies choose a different moment for the starting point of measuring time to fill. Other options besides having approved a job requisition include:

- a hiring manager submitting a job requisition for approval
- publishing a job opening online

Similarly, some organizations consider the starting date as the end of time to fill.

What's the value of measuring Time to Fill?

- **Data is only useful if it is actionable and applied.** The value of measuring time to fill is in its application to business planning and improving HR processes. Some of the benefits of tracking this metric are:
- **It enables you to plan your recruitment efforts better.** By measuring time to fill, you understand on average how long it takes to replace someone with similar experience. As an example, let's say you are replacing a senior economist. After doing the calculation, you understand that it takes 45 days to fill this vacancy. This then allows you to start recruitment efforts at the right time. You're also able

to build contingency plans during the time the role is vacant. It allows you to plan onboarding and handover procedures more effectively too.

- **Resolving inefficiencies in your recruitment process.** As you continue to track this metric, you will be able to spot areas of inefficiencies in recruitment and streamline your strategy. You'll start to understand which roles take longer to fill and which departments take longer to fill a position. You also get a grasp on which talent source is the most effective. For example, some roles are filled faster with an agency, whereas other roles are best filled with a LinkedIn job ad. Time to fill will provide you with the answers as to which is the most effective source.
- **Reducing the cost of unfilled positions.** Time to fill helps an organization save money. Firstly, place job adverts cost money; the less time a role is advertised, the greater your savings. Secondly, when a role is vacant, it costs money to pay employees to work overtime. It also increases burnout and stress in the workplace, which is in the long term a very high cost. Finally, the longer it takes to hire someone, the lower your customer satisfaction is likely to be, which affects the company's overall performance and profits.

How do you measure Time to Fill?

Remember, when calculating time to fill, you need to adjust the metric to what makes sense for your company.

It is an excellent metric for business planning. Time to fill offers you a realistic view of how long it will replace a departed employee. It helps you plan your hiring efforts better and serves as a warning when your hiring process takes too long. In addition, it has a positive net effect on everyone's time, as it means less overtime and greater stability.

It is also a crucial measurement for your recruitment experience, as 23% of candidates lose interest in an employer if they don't hear back within one week. A further 46% become disinterested if they don't hear anything within 1-2 weeks.

Your formula would be:

The number of calendar days between the starting point (manager approves role or day job is advertised) and the endpoint (date that candidate accepts the job offer or until the first day of onboarding).

For example, if Company X advertised the role of a marketing manager on 1 January and decided to use the 'advertising date' as the start point. The candidate then

accepts the offer and starts on 1 March (onboarding date is used as the endpoint). The time to fill this role is 60 days. As an organization, you need to be consistent in your choices of starting and endpoint – this is so that you can have consistent data and compare it against relevant benchmarks.

To calculate average Time to Fill:

Average Time to Fill Formula

Your average time to fill provides you with general insights across different roles.

As an example, let's say you hired five administrators at your organization, and it took you 15, 60, 10, 30, and 40 days to hire them, respectively; your calculation would look like this:

Average Time to Fill Calculation Example:

Your average time to hire would then be 31 days.

- You can also make further calculations to measure the effectiveness of your recruitment process on various benchmarks. As an example, you could calculate time to fill: per quarter: which would be sum of time to fill for all positions in the quarter / number of positions filled in the quarter, and annually: which would be sum of time to fill for all positions for the year / number of positions filled in the year.
- Calculating time to fill per role and department. When measuring time to fill, you need to consider your needs and various metrics. For example, it is likely to take longer to hire a senior data scientist on average than it is to hire a contact center agent. Therefore, the average time to hire would look different for these two roles. Similarly, your average time to hire would look different when comparing departments (IT vs. legal department). It is best practice to measure against similar roles and departments, as it is a more accurate representation of how long it takes to fill a position.

Time to Hire Human Resource Management (HRM) Metric:

Time to Hire is what amount of time it requires for a Human Resources gathering to enroll a picked job candidate. It gauges the speed and efficiency of your HR bunch and can be an indication of competition in the utilizing market. Also, a compelling HRM technique for assessing the efficiency of a Human Resources Team is to look at measure of time its expectation to enroll a contender. This estimation can help you with understanding how well the gathering executes when the right candidate applies, including how quickly HR recognizes them and how extended it takes for the competitor to recognize the suggestion. This estimation may moreover decide if there's a

bottleneck in your utilizing cycle and how quickly your HR bunch drops when they track down the right competitor for a position. Understanding deficiencies can help you with seeking after the most ideal decisions to additionally foster your utilizing cycle. Stood out from the Time to Fill, which can be use as often as possible in 30 days or more, the HRM cycle will also need to move fast, at whatever point they perceived with the ideal newbie. The management capacity on the hand doesn't remain accessible in an HR decision for quite a while, but the cycle and the HRM readiness and openness for utilizing managers needs to compliment the business executives always.

Basis	Time to Hire	Time to Fill
Questions	How many days does it takes the Human Resource to hire qualified candidates for the said job vacancies?	How long is the whole recruitment process, from the job creation and to hiring a newbie?
Starting Point	The first applicant during the application process	Job creation, including job opening and job advertisement
Information about	Selection Process	Recruitment Process
Purpose	Abe to see the efficiency of the whole recruitment process.	The purpose is to plan first an HR hiring process.
Length	Shorter	Longer

Table 1. Differences between Time to Hire and Time to Fill HR Metric

Part 2. Human Resource Management (HRM) Metric: Return on Investment

Measuring the Return on Investment (ROI) in a given Human Resource Planning to every schools, colleges and universities has its own challenges and collaborative effort. Also to mention the culture and diversity of a given institutions, and considers their HR metric as a comparative concept of ROI across to other academic businesses. But there is always one global purpose that measures ROI, every firm considers profit development and utilizations from their business operations. As for the concept of human resource, ROI simply describes as a measurement on how recruitment and selection are very useful and beneficial to employees. In addition, getting human resource ROI in most academic institutions are very useful, because it concerns of putting a career investment from their employees

Selecting a ROI model that is fit-to-purpose for human resource, and suits the type of data available is imperative in order to produce useful and practical information. The decision is to include social or economic returns will always influence your choice, along with adopting an evaluative (actual return) or forecasting (potential return) perspective. For example, the Cost-Benefit Analysis assigns monetary value to training

costs to determine the cost-benefit ration, the Social Return on Investment approach has a stakeholder-driven evaluation with a strong focus on social impact, while the net Present Value model compares the value of money now to the value in the future. Ultimately, a ROI model must add value and measure the factors that matter to the stakeholders **UNESCO and NCVER, 2020**.

Return on Investment Indicators from a Job and Non-Job employment activities:
UNESCO and NCVER, 2020

INDICATOR	MEASURE	EXAMPLES OF MEASURES
1.) Employability Skills	Attainment of employability skills for those who have completed training	Attainment of employable skills and knowledge that are required to get a job and participate effectively in the workforce. This include communication, self-management, planning, teamwork, decision-making and problem solving.
2.) Employment	Employment rate of those not employed before training	Proportional employment scale who are considered employed at the end of training or job orientation.
3.) Improved Employment Status	Improved employment status of those employed before training who have completed training	Proportional improvement scale towards employment status and other employment circumstances. For example, casual to permanent status; part-time status to full-time status; or promoted to a higher level of employment.
4.) Wages/Earnings	Income of full-time workers after training	Employment earnings of those employed full-time after such training or orientation. It also measure by gross net earnings, gross monthly earnings, weekly earnings, pre-tax hourly wages or annual earnings.
5.) Entrepreneurship	Attain of entrepreneurial skills and knowledge	Attainment of skills, knowledge and attributes that aim to build an

		entrepreneurial mindset and skillset required to transform ideas into action.
--	--	---

Table 2. Job related ROI indicator and measurement for employed individuals

INDICATOR	MEASURE	EXAMPLES OF MEASURE
1.) Well-Being	Employees that have an improved sense of well-being after training or orientation.	Improved self-esteem Improved confidence Life/work satisfaction Self-rated health Satisfy financial capabilities
2.) Foundation skill gains	Employees that have an improved foundation skills after their training or orientation.	Attainment to language literacy, numerical skills, and financial literacy
3.) Socio-economic status	An improved socio-economic status of employees after the completion of their work / training.	Proportional employment, positive changes to employment status, household income, remoted living standards.
4.) Social inclusion	Participation in social and team building groups or campus communities.	Membership of a club or an organization or social network group, volunteering, & association.

Table 3. Non-Job related ROI indicator and measurement for employed individuals

Calculating the return on investment for human capital is complex. It requires you to allocate a financial benefit to a human capital initiative. This is not always as straightforward because how do you actually know that, for example, a learning intervention directly contributed towards an increase in revenue? There are so many variables that could affect the outcome, including market volatility, change in conditions, and even luck. The ROI Institute, however, developed a model that is able to accurately calculate HCROI. **Vulpen. E.V. (2022)**

Before we go for a sample Human Capital Return on Investment (HCROI) computations, the following are the main steps in gathering data information:
Vulpen. E.V. (2022)

Step #1 – Evaluation planning

This is the part to clearly define the objectives of your human capital initiative. For example: “Hire three IT network developers” or “Implement a talent exchange program

in the marketing department” or “Achieve an Employee Net Promoter Score of +20”.

Step #2 – Data collection

This is the collection of data pre, during, and after implementing an HC program or action. During this period, you may collect human capital metrics: hard data (which you can do via HC systems) and soft data (which you can gather in employee satisfaction surveys, on-the-job observation, etc.).

Step #3 – Data analysis

To calculate ROI of human capital, this is one of the most important steps. You need to analyze data on two fronts:

Step #4 – Isolate the effects of the HC initiative or program

This is important because many factors can influence performance, and you want to specifically measure the impact of human capital. There are many ways to do this, including launching a pilot program, using trend lines to show differences, customer input, external stakeholder feedback, and using subject matter experts to analyze effects.

Step #5 – Convert HC data to financial output

This requires the cost of every human capital program to be accounted for and given a value. This is situation-dependent. As an example, due to a training program, an employee might develop an additional product. That additional product is thus converted to a profit or cost-saving, depending on the initiative’s outcome.

Once you have followed the above steps, you will have enough information to calculate the financial return with this formula:

$$\text{HCROI} = \frac{\text{Net Benefits} - \text{Cost}}{\text{Cost}}$$

Suppose you roll out a “Campus Job Fair” initiatives in the workplace, costing approximately Php 250,000 good for 5 days. Those are your human capital expenses. The savings for (reduction in stress, absenteeism, burnout, etc.) made this initiative amounts to Php 700,000. Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{HCROI} &= \text{Php } 700,000 - \text{Php } 250,000 / \text{Php } 250,000 \\ &= 2 \text{ (which is represented as a ratio 2:1)} \end{aligned}$$

This means that for every Php 1 you spent on the wellness program, there was a benefit of Php 2. There are variables you need to consider, of course, when analyzing things in this way (for example, the measurement period of the cost-saving). As long as the data and time frame are consistent, this is a highly effective way to calculate HCROI.

Now let’s say that the HR team decides to invest an additional Php 10,000 in the

Campus Job Fair, it will result for an additional saving investment of Php 150,000. Now let's look for the computation of HCROI:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{HCROI} &= \text{Php } 850,000 - \text{Php } 260,000 / \text{Php } 260,000 \\ &= 2.27 \text{ (which is represented as a ratio 2.27:1)}\end{aligned}$$

So the investment of additional Php 10,000, that's an additional benefit of 0.26. For the long period of time, the value saved is almost insurmountable. By using this HCROI formula, it is a great way for HR planning and business reflecting. The long-term effects for investments will be a bit more into your human capital and have a financial performance of the organization.

Benefits of using the human capital ROI as a metric and KPI:

- **Understanding the impact of your human capital initiatives.** You can see what results your initiatives bring. That way, all your decisions are data-based, and every dollar spent can be accounted for.
- **Showing tangible results of HC initiatives to the leadership.** Essentially, you're able to quantify the business impact of your efforts and show it to the leadership. For example, you're able to directly translate the results of HC initiatives such as a "talent exchange program" to the financial impact on the business.
- **Identifying and filling the gaps in human capital.** The data helps you understand where your organization is excelling and where it lacks in terms of human capital. You're able to clearly see through data what adding or subtracting human capital will have on the business outcome.
- **Improve your HC processes.** Through a variety of feedback mechanisms received as a result of calculating ROI, you're able to improve your human capital management practices and processes. Along the way, you're able to make adjustments (in real-time as well) and understand specifically which part of the HC process needs improvements.
- **Eliminate ineffective HC processes.** You're also able to close or remove any human capital initiatives that are not effective. If, for example, a talent exchange program is yielding no financial benefits after five years, you're able to close the program or make adjustments along the way. Either way, you're able to cut down on costs.

Part 3. Human Resource Management (HRM) Metric: Employee Productivity

KRA 1: Content Knowledge and Pedagogy (DepEd Philippines)

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION (MOV)	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (4)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
1. Applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas	<p>Classroom Observation Tool (COT) rating sheet or inter-observer agreement form from</p> <p>1. an online observation of online synchronous teaching</p> <p>2. <i>if option 1 is not possible</i>, an observation of a video lesson that is SLM- based or MELC- aligned</p> <p>3. <i>if options 1 and 2 are not possible</i>, an observation of a demonstration teaching</p> <p>via LAC</p>	Quality	Demonstrated Level 7 in Objective 1 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 6 in Objective 1 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 5 in Objective 1 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 4 in Objective 1 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 3 in Objective 1 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms or No acceptable evidence was shown

Note: For this objective, two MOVs are required for the entire school year. In computing the rating for Quality: (i) get the corresponding RPMS 5-point scale rating of each COT rating; (ii) calculate the average of the RPMS ratings; and (iii) find the transmuted RPMS rating.

Example:

Means of Verification (MOV)	COT Rating	RPMS 5point Scale Rating	Average	RPMS Rating for Quality
COT Rating Sheet 1	6		3.500	4 (Very Satisfactory)
COT Rating Sheet 2	5			

RPMS Rating Transmutation Table	
Outstanding (5)	4.500-5.000
Very Satisfactory (4)	3.500-4.499
Satisfactory (3)	2.500-3.499
Unsatisfactory (2)	1.500-2.499
Poor (1)	1.000-1.499

KRA 1: Content Knowledge and Pedagogy (DepEd Philippines)

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION (MOV)	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (4)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
2. Ensured the positive use of ICT to facilitate the teaching and learning process	<p>Any supplementary material (in print/digital format) made by the ratee and used in the lesson delivery that highlights the positive use of ICT to facilitate the teaching and learning process</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activity sheet/s One lesson from a self-learning module (SLM) Lesson plan (e.g., DLP, DLL, WHLP, WLP, WLL, Lesson Exemplars, and the likes) Video lesson Audio lesson Other learning materials in print/digital format (please specify and provide annotations) 	Quality	Ensured that the ICT used redefine and transform learning experiences and are documented properly and consistently using any referencing style as shown in the submitted learning material	Ensured that the ICT used augment and enrich learning experiences and are documented properly and consistently using any referencing style as shown in the submitted learning material	Ensured that the ICT used modify processes and improve learning experiences and are documented properly and consistently using any referencing style as shown in the submitted learning material	Ensured that ICT are used but do not create a new learning experience and/or are documented but not consistent with one referencing style as shown in the submitted learning material	No acceptable evidence was shown

*The following terms adapted Ruben Puentedura's SAMR Model (substitution, augmenting, modification, and redefining) in technology integration: (i) ICT used "redefine and transform" learning experiences

– The learning materials are able to create new kinds of learning experiences that were not possible before, e.g., using social networking sites to engage with other students from other corners of the globe;

(ii) ICT used "augment and enrich" learning experiences – The use of the tool provides value-added experience, e.g., using Google Jamboard that makes discussion interactive; (iii) ICT used "modify processes and improve" learning experiences – Using ICT improves processes to increase productivity, e.g., using Google Docs for real time collaboration in group activities.

Note: For this objective, two MOVs are required for the entire school year. In computing the rating for Quality, calculate the average rating of the two MOV and find the transmuted RPMS rating.

Example:

Means of Verification (MOV)	RPMS 5-point Scale Rating	Average	RPMS Rating for Quality
MOV 1: Activity Sheet	3	3.500	4 (Very Satisfactory)
MOV 2: One lesson from a SLM	4		

RPMS Rating Transmutation Table	
Outstanding (5)	4.500-5.000
Very Satisfactory (4)	3.500-4.499
Satisfactory (3)	2.500-3.499
Unsatisfactory (2)	1.500-2.499
Poor (1)	1.000-1.499

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION (MOV)	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (4)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
3. Applied a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills	<p><i>Any supplementary material (in print/digital format) made by the ratee and used in the lesson delivery</i> that highlights teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity sheet/s • One lesson from a self-learning module (SLM) • Lesson plan (e.g., DLP, DLL, WHLP, WLP, WLL, Lesson Exemplars, and the likes) • Video lesson • Audio lesson • Other learning materials in print/digital format (please specify and provide annotations) 	Quality	Applied teaching strategies that challenge learners to draw conclusions and justify their thinking or put parts together to promote deeper understanding of ideas learned as shown in the submitted learning material	Applied teaching strategies that require learners to make connections using ideas learned as shown in the submitted learning material	Applied teaching strategies that require learners to describe and explain ideas learned as shown in the submitted learning material	Applied teaching strategies that lead learners along a single path of inquiry and/or to simple recall and rote memorization of concepts as shown in the submitted learning material	No acceptable evidence was shown

*The following phrases are defined in terms of Lorin Anderson's revised categories of the cognitive domain under the Bloom's Taxonomy: "put parts together" refers to *Creating* (synthesizing parts into something new to form a functional whole); "draw conclusions and justify their thinking" refers to *Evaluating* (making judgments about the value of ideas or materials); "make connections using ideas learned" refers to *Analyzing* (determining how parts relate); "describe and explain ideas learned" refers to *Applying* (applying information and skills to related ideas/concepts/materials) and *Understanding* (constructing meaning); and "single path of inquiry" and "simple recall and rote memorization" refer to *Remembering* (using memory to retrieve/recall ideas).

Note: For this objective, two MOVs are required for the entire school year. In computing the rating for Quality, calculate the average rating of the two MOV and find the transmuted RPMS rating.

Example:

Means of Verification (MOV)	RPMS 5-point Scale Rating	Average	RPMS Rating for Quality
MOV 1: Activity Sheet	3	3.500	4 (Very Satisfactory)
MOV 2: One lesson from a SLM	4		

RPMS Rating Transmutation Table	
Outstanding (5)	4.500-5.000
Very Satisfactory (4)	3.500-4.499
Satisfactory (3)	2.500-3.499
Unsatisfactory (2)	1.500-2.499
Poor (1)	1.000-1.499

KRA 2: Diversity of Learners & Assessment and Reporting (DepEd Philippines)

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION (MOV)	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (4)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
4. Established a learner-centered culture by using teaching strategies that respond to their linguistic, cultural, socioeconomic and religious backgrounds	<p><i>Any supplementary material (in print/digital format) made by the ratee and used in the lesson delivery</i> that highlights teaching strategies that are responsive to learners' linguistic, cultural, socioeconomic, or religious backgrounds</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity sheet/s • One lesson from a self-learning module (SLM) • Lesson plan (e.g., DLP, DLL, WHLP, WLP, WLL, Lesson Exemplars, and the likes) • Video lesson • Audio lesson • Other learning materials in print/digital format (please specify and provide annotations) 	Quality	Utilized effective teaching strategies that are appropriate in responding to learners' linguistic, cultural, socioeconomic, or religious backgrounds at an individual level* as shown in the submitted learning material	Utilized effective teaching strategies that are appropriate in responding to learners' linguistic, cultural, socioeconomic, or religious backgrounds at a group level* as shown in the submitted learning material	Utilized an effective teaching strategy that is appropriate in responding to learners' linguistic, cultural, socioeconomic, or religious backgrounds as shown in the submitted learning material	Utilized a teaching strategy or strategies that partially respond to learners' linguistic, cultural, socioeconomic, or religious backgrounds as shown in the submitted learning material	No acceptable evidence was shown

* "At a group level" refers to general, whole class instruction where teaching/modelling of concepts for all students happen at once; "at an individual level" refers to targeted instruction to an individual learner or to a number of learners.

Note: For this objective, two MOVs are required for the entire school year. In computing the rating for Quality, calculate the average rating of the two MOV and find the transmuted RPMS rating.

Example:

Means of Verification (MOV)	RPMS 5-point Scale Rating	Average	RPMS Rating for Quality
MOV 1: Activity Sheet	3	3.500	4 (Very Satisfactory)
MOV 2: One lesson from a SLM	4		

RPMS Rating Transmutation Table	
Outstanding (5)	4.500-5.000
Very Satisfactory (4)	3.500-4.499
Satisfactory (3)	2.500-3.499
Unsatisfactory (2)	1.500-2.499
Poor (1)	1.000-1.499

KRA 2: Diversity of Learners & Assessment and Reporting (DepEd Philippines)

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION (MOV)	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (4)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
<p>5. Planned and delivered teaching strategies that are responsive to the special educational needs of learners in difficult circumstances*, including: geographic isolation; chronic illness; displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement or disasters; child abuse and child labor practices</p>	<p>Classroom Observation Tool (COT) rating sheet or inter-observer agreement form from</p> <p>1. an online observation of online synchronous teaching</p> <p>2. <i>if option 1 is not possible</i>, an observation of a video lesson that is SLM-based or MELC- aligned</p> <p>3. <i>if options 1 and 2 are not possible</i>, an observation of a demonstration teaching via LAC</p>	Quality	Demonstrated Level 7 in Objective 5 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 6 in Objective 5 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 5 in Objective 5 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 4 in Objective 5 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 3 in Objective 5 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms or No acceptable evidence was shown

* This objective is about strategies that respond to “learners in difficult circumstances” (see glossary for the definition). In the context of SY 2020-2021, the Filipino learners (and all the learners across the globe) have been affected by the COVID-19 pandemic which brought difficulty in the way they learn and live. The efforts that teachers exert to adjust and modify the teaching and learning delivery is captured in this year’s RPMS.

Note: For this objective, two MOVs are required for the entire school year. In computing the rating for Quality: (i) get the corresponding RPMS 5-point scale rating of each COT rating; (ii) calculate the average of the RPMS ratings; and (iii) find the transmuted RPMS rating.

Example:

Means of Verification (MOV)	COT Rating	RPMS 5-point Scale Rating	Average	RPMS Rating for Quality
COT Rating Sheet 1	6	4	3.500	4 (Very Satisfactory)
COT Rating Sheet 2	5	3		

RPMS Rating Transmutation Table	
Outstanding (5)	4.500-5.000
Very Satisfactory (4)	3.500-4.499
Satisfactory (3)	2.500-3.499
Unsatisfactory (2)	1.500-2.499
Poor (1)	1.000-1.499

KRA 2: Diversity of Learners & Assessment and Reporting (DepEd Philippines)

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION (MOV)	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (4)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
6. Used strategies for providing timely, accurate and constructive feedback to improve learner performance	<i>Evidence that highlights providing accurate and constructive feedback</i> to improve learner performance and that <i>shows timeliness of feedback</i> given to any of the following <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • activity sheet • performance task • quiz or test • self-learning module 	Quality	Provided learners with accurate, and specific and directed constructive feedback* as shown in the evidence submitted	Provided learners with accurate, and specific constructive feedback as shown in the evidence submitted	Provided learners with accurate, and general constructive feedback as shown in the evidence submitted	Provided learners with inaccurate and/or destructive feedback as shown in the evidence submitted	No evidence was shown
		Timeliness	MOV submitted shows feedback given within 5 working days from submission**	MOV submitted shows feedback given within 6-10 working days from submission**	MOV submitted shows feedback given within 11-20 working days from submission**	MOV submitted shows feedback given beyond 20 working days from submission**	No evidence was shown

Feedback* refers to essential and culturally-appropriate written and/or oral **information about learners' performance/output that can be used to raise awareness on their strengths and weaknesses as bases for improvement; **Directed constructive feedback** is constructive feedback that gives specific direction on how to make improvements; **Specific constructive feedback** is constructive feedback that points out a specific issue in a learner's performance/output; **General constructive feedback** is constructive feedback that points out what is commonly observed among learners' performance/output (and is addressed to the class in general).

***All MOVs for this objective must contain date stamps to keep track of submission of learners' output/performance and of the learners' receipt of teachers' feedback.*

Note: For this objective, two MOVs are required for the entire school year. In computing the rating for Quality, calculate the average rating of the two MOV and find the transmuted RPMS rating. Follow the same procedure in calculating the rating for Timeliness.

Example:

Means of Verification (MOV)	RPMS 5-point Scale Rating for Quality	RPMS 5-point Scale Rating for Timeliness
MOV 1: Activity sheet with teachers' feedback	3	5
MOV 2: Performance task with teachers' feedback	4	5
Average	3.500	5.000
RPMS Rating	4 (Very Satisfactory)	5 (Outstanding)

RPMS Rating Transmutation Table	
Outstanding (5)	4.500-5.000
Very Satisfactory (4)	3.500-4.499
Satisfactory (3)	2.500-3.499
Unsatisfactory (2)	1.500-2.499
Poor (1)	1.000-1.499

KRA 3: Curriculum and Planning (DepEd Philippines)

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION (MOV)	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (4)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
7. Selected, developed, organized and used appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals	Classroom Observation Tool (COT) rating sheet or inter-observer agreement form from 1. an online observation of online synchronous teaching 2. <i>if option 1 is not possible</i> , an observation of a video lesson that is SLM-based or MELC-aligned 3. <i>if options 1 and 2 are not possible</i> , an observation of a demonstration teaching via LAC	Quality	Demonstrated Level 7 in Objective 7 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 6 in Objective 7 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 5 in Objective 7 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 4 in Objective 7 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms	Demonstrated Level 3 in Objective 7 as shown in COT rating sheets/inter-observer agreement forms or No acceptable evidence was shown

Note: For this objective, two MOVs are required for the entire school year. In computing the rating for Quality: (i) get the corresponding RPMS 5-point scale rating of each COT rating; (ii) calculate the average of the RPMS ratings; and (iii) find the transmuted RPMS rating.

Example:

Means of Verification (MOV)	COT Rating	RPMS 5-point Scale Rating	Average	RPMS Rating for Quality
COT Rating Sheet 1	6	4	3.500	4 (Very Satisfactory)
COT Rating Sheet 2	5	3		

RPMS Rating Transmutation Table	
Outstanding (5)	4.500-5.000
Very Satisfactory (4)	3.500-4.499
Satisfactory (3)	2.500-3.499
Unsatisfactory (2)	1.500-2.499
Poor (1)	1.000-1.499

KRA 3: Curriculum and Planning (DepEd Philippines)

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (4)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
<p>8. Set achievable and appropriate learning outcomes that are aligned with learning competencies</p>	<p>One lesson plan (e.g., DLP, DLL, WHLP, WLP, WLL, Lesson Exemplars, and the likes) or one lesson from a self-learning module prepared by the ratee with achievable and appropriate learning outcomes that are aligned with the learning competencies as shown in any of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lecture/discussion • Activity/activity sheet • Performance task • Rubric for assessing performance using criteria that appropriately describe the target output 	<p>Quality</p>	<p>All of the learning outcomes set are aligned with the learning competencies as shown in the MOV submitted</p>	<p>Majority of the learning outcomes set are aligned with the learning competencies as shown in the MOV submitted</p>	<p>Half of the learning outcomes set are aligned with the learning competencies as shown in the MOV submitted</p>	<p>Less than half of the learning outcomes set are aligned with the learning competencies as shown in the MOV submitted</p>	<p>No acceptable evidence was shown</p>

KRA 3: Curriculum and Planning (DepEd Philippines)

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION (MOV)	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (3)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
9. Built relationships with parents/guardians and the wider school community to facilitate involvement in the educative process	1. Proof of participation in any activity for improved access to education such as, but not limited to the ff. activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distribution of learning materials to learners/parents (e.g., receipt form/monitoring form during distribution of learning materials, etc.) • Brigada Eskwela (e.g., commitment form to stakeholders, developed advocacy materials, certificate of participation that involves parents'/stakeholders' engagement signed by the school head, etc.) • Home visitation (e.g., home visitation form, etc.) • Others (please specify and provide annotations) 2. Parent-teacher log or proof of other stakeholders meeting (e.g., one-on-one parent-teacher- learner conference log; attendance sheet with minutes of online or face-to-face meeting; proof of involvement in the learners'/parents' orientation, etc.) 3. Any form of communication to parents/stakeholders (e.g., notice of meeting; screenshot of chat/text message/communication with parent/guardian [name or any identifier removed]; digital/ printed copy of Learner Enrollment Survey Form signed by the ICT Coordinator/Focal person and School Head)	Quality	Sustained engagement with parents/guardians and/or wider school community to facilitate involvement in the educative process as evidenced by 2 or more of MOV no. 1 or 2	Secured collaboration with parents/guardians and/or wider school community to facilitate involvement in the educative process as evidenced by one MOV no. 1 or 2	Communicated with and obtained response from parents/guardians and/or wider school community to facilitate involvement in the educative process as evidenced by MOV No. 3	Communicated with parents/guardians and/or wider school community to facilitate involvement in the educative process but received no response/reply as evidenced by MOV No. 3	No acceptable evidence was shown
		Efficiency	Submitted any 4 of the acceptable MOV*	Submitted any 3 of the acceptable MOV*	Submitted any 2 of the acceptable MOV*	Submitted any 1 of the acceptable MOV	No acceptable evidence was shown

* "Any 4/3/2 of the acceptable MOV" under Efficiency means the same kind of MOV can be submitted more than once (e.g., Submitted MOVs could be two (2) Parent-teacher logs, one (1) printed LESF, and one (1) screenshot of correspondence with parents via an online platform to merit an Outstanding in Efficiency for this objective.)

KRA 4: Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development **(DepEd Philippines)**

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION (MOV)	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (4)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
10. Participated in professional networks to share knowledge and to enhance practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Certificate of completion in a course/training • Certificate of participation in a webinar, retooling, upskilling, and other training/ seminar/ workshop with proof of implementation • Certificate of recognition/ speakership in a webinar, retooling, upskilling, and other training/ seminar/ workshop • Any proof of participation to a benchmarking activity • Any proof of participation in school LAC sessions (online/face-to-face) certified by the LAC Coordinator • Others (please specify and provide annotations) 	Quality	Participated in any professional network/activity that requires output* and proof of implementation ** within the school to share knowledge and to enhance practice as evidenced by the submitted MOV	Participated in any professional network/activity that requires output* and proof of implementation ** within the department/ grade level to share knowledge and to enhance practice as evidenced by the submitted MOV	Participated in any professional network/activity that requires output* to share knowledge and to enhance practice as evidenced by the submitted MOV	Participated in any professional network/activity that does not require output to share knowledge and to enhance practice as evidenced by the submitted MOV	No acceptable evidence was shown
		Efficiency	Submitted 4 different kinds of acceptable MOV***	Submitted 3 different kinds of acceptable MOV***	Submitted 2 different kinds of acceptable MOV***	Submitted any 1 of the acceptable MOV	No acceptable evidence was shown

* "Output" may include, but not limited to, lesson plan, instructional materials, action plan, or any teaching and learning-related materials.

** "Proof of implementation" can be in the form of implemented action plan, lesson plan executed in class, application project, etc.

*** "Different kinds of acceptable MOV" under Efficiency means each type of MOV can be submitted only once

(e.g. Submitted MOVs could be one (1) Certificate of participation in a webinar, one (1) Certificate of recognition/ speakership in a conference, one (1) proof of participation in a benchmarking activity, and one (1) proof of participation in school LAC session).

KRA 4: Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development **(DepEd Philippines)**

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION (MOV)	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (4)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
11. Developed a personal improvement plan based on reflection of one's practice and ongoing professional learning	<p>Main MOV:</p> <p>Individual Performance and Commitment Review Form-Development Plan (IPCRF- DP)</p> <p>Supporting MOV:</p> <p>Any document aligned with the IPCRF-DP such as</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflection of one's practice during LAC session/s with proof of attendance • Reflection/Personal Notes on Coaching and Mentoring and/or Mid- year Review 	Quality	Updated the Development Plan and approved by the rater during Phase II of the RPMS cycle	Discussed progress on the Development Plan with the rater to check whether Development Needs were addressed	Accomplished the Development Plan from learning objectives up to resources needed to address Development Needs during Phase I of the RPMS cycle	Accomplished the Strengths and Development Needs portion of the Development Plan after self-assessment at the beginning of the school year	No acceptable evidence was shown
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal notes journal on division/school-led INSET with proof of attendance • Certificate of enrolment/ registration form/class card in graduate/post-graduate school/online courses • Any learning material highlighting the improvement done based on accomplished "reflection" section • Others (Please specify and provide annotations) 		Efficiency	Submitted the IPCRF-DP with any 4 of the acceptable Supporting MOV*	Submitted the IPCRF-DP with any 3 of the acceptable Supporting MOV*	Submitted the IPCRF-DP with any 2 of the acceptable Supporting MOV*	Submitted the IPCRF-DP with any 1 of the acceptable Supporting MOV

* "Any 4/3/2 of the acceptable Supporting MOV" under Efficiency means the same kind of MOV can be submitted more than once (e.g., Submitted MOVs could be two (2) Reflection on LAC sessions with proof of attendance and two (2) Reflection/Personal Notes on Coaching and Mentoring to merit an Outstanding in Efficiency under this objective).

KRA 5: Plus Factor (DepEd Philippines)

OBJECTIVE	MEANS OF VERIFICATION (MOV)	PERFORMANCE INDICATOR					
		QET	Outstanding (5)	Very Satisfactory (4)	Satisfactory (3)	Unsatisfactory (2)	Poor (1)
12. Performed various related works/activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process	Proof of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> committee involvement advisorship of co-curricular activities involvement as module/learning material writer involvement as module/learning material validator participation in the RO/SDO/school-initiated TV-/radio-based instruction book or journal authorship/contributorship coordinatorship/chairpersonship coaching and mentoring learners in competitions mentoring pre-service teachers participation in demonstration teaching participation as research presenter in a forum/conference others (please specify and provide annotations) 	Quality	Performed at least 1 related work/activity that contributed to the teaching-learning process beyond the school/Community Learning Center (CLC) as evidenced by submitted MOV	Performed at least 1 related work/activity that contributed to the teaching-learning process within the school/Community Learning Center (CLC) as evidenced by submitted MOV	Performed at least 1 related work/activity that contributed to the teaching-learning process within the learning area/department as evidenced by submitted MOV	Performed at least 1 related work/activity that contributed to the teaching-learning process within the class as evidenced by submitted MOV	No acceptable evidence was shown
		Efficiency	Submitted any 4 of the acceptable MOV*	Submitted any 3 of the acceptable MOV*	Submitted any 2 of the acceptable MOV*	Submitted any 1 of the acceptable MOV	No acceptable evidence was shown

* "Any 4/3/2 of the acceptable MOV" under Efficiency means the same kind of MOV can be submitted *more than once*.

Organizations today are facing the question of how to accurately measure productivity, particularly as the world becomes more and more remote. Furthermore, the question of measuring productivity has moved beyond measuring a simple 'output.' It is nuanced, taking into account external and internal factors and the organization's needs at a particular given point. Organizations and employees have always searched for ways to generate the greatest amount of output in the shortest space of time. And to demonstrate this, you have to be able to measure it. **Vulpen, E.V. (2022)**

Why calculate productivity in the workplace? **Vulpen, E.V. (2022)**

Productivity is a metric that helps you understand when and how your business needs to adjust to achieve better results. Let's take a deeper dive into some other reasons why calculating productivity is essential:

- **Workforce optimization** – Calculating productivity helps an organization understand their current workforce and make changes along the way in the face of changes. It provides the data to make tweaks to employee work schedules and organizational structure, reduce operational costs, and optimize employee performance.
- **Creating financial impact** – Calculating productivity is equivalent to keeping a finger on your organization's pulse. In the changing market, you're able to adjust employee processes or workflow to optimize for performance. As a result, you're always able to ensure an organization is in the best position to increase profit while maintaining the same level of effort.
- **Tracking changes to productivity** – You're able to see if anything changed and take action where necessary. Furthermore, you're also able to be aware of any signals that could lead to irrecoverable damage.
- **Managing your business** – A firm understanding of your organization's productivity levels allows for better decision-making. You're able to manage the front line of your business and customer expectations. It also identifies areas of concern in operations and whether or not you need to expand your team or implement a new operating model.

To calculate productivity, the formula is:

$$\text{Productivity} = \text{Output} / \text{Input}$$

Example #1:

Let's take, for example, an organization that produces laptops. In one month, they make over 200,000 laptops, with 40 employees, working 18 days and 9 hours per day over a period of 6 months.

Details	#1
No. of laptops	200,000
No. of labor hours per day	9
Months	6
No. of days worked in a month	18
Number of employees	40

To work out your total input, do the following calculation:

Input = 40 (# of employees) x 9 (# of hours of work per day) x 6 (# of months) x 18 (# of days worked in a month).

That's 38,880.

Productivity = 200,000 / 38,880 = **5.14**

That means for every hour, 5.14 of output was produced. In other words, the company produced 5.14 laptops every hour.

Example #2:

Now, let's say the organization decided to hire an operations manager that optimizes processes and the workflow. This leads to a more significant increase in the number of laptops produced but maintains the same amount of effort. As a result, the data reflects the following:

Details	#
No. of laptops	270,000
No. of labor hours per day	9
Months	6
No. of days worked in a month	18
Number of employees	41

As a result, your output would be 6.8.

That's a difference of 1.66 in productivity produced just as a result of one hire. You can see how having the data in front of you and one change or tweak can significantly impact the overall productivity numbers and total output.

Considerations when calculating productivity: Vulpen, E.V. (2022)

- **Industry factors** – Consider that not all industries operate in the same way. In environments such as manufacturing or sales, where it is easy to represent productivity in numbers, it is easy to measure productivity. As an example, the IFC presents that the global metric for a customer service call to be answered is within 20 seconds at least 80% of the time. These all have nuances, as certain industries are more complex than others. Some industries, however, have measured are not as tangible. This is where using management by objectives or 360-degree feedback becomes useful.

- **Organizational targets and benchmarks** – It is possible to use external benchmarks to measure workforce productivity. This might be represented, for example, the average number of sales made per hour in a particular industry or the drop-off rate for sales calls. However, this does not apply to all jobs. Again, for service-related jobs, you may want to establish internal benchmarks and organizational targets.
- **Efficiency (and how it differs from productivity)** – It's essential to establish a clear difference between productivity and efficiency—both of these need to be calculated. Productivity is an indicator of output over time, but efficiency indicates how well a task is completed. For example, an employee might be able to develop three sales presentations in one week, whereas another might create 20 sales presentations in the same period of time.

How to improve productivity? **Vulpen, E.V. (2022)**

- **Use technology to automate repetitive tasks** – In HR, for example, automation can include interview scheduling, onboarding document signing flows, etc. At the same time that tasks are automated, upskill employees in other way. Again, in HR, that could mean helping them develop their business acumen or their HR strategy & leadership skills. That way, you can ensure a productivity increase.
- **Work on employee engagement** – Engagement and productivity go hand in hand. So if you want to make sure that your employees are productive, you have to continuously work on employee engagement. Research shows that engaged employees are up to 17% more productive than their peers. That's quite a considerable difference if you calculate that across an entire organization.
- **Clearly define what productivity means for each role/team** – Everyone must understand what it means to be productive. It also includes setting clear goals. This will be vastly different across roles, and based on that, the ways you measure productivity will also differ (as we've discussed above).

Furthermore, consider doing an annual inventory on productivity in the workplace. Take a step back, and look at how all parts of the organization fit together. It might also be helpful to hire an external analyst to provide an objective view of what is working and barriers to productivity. That way, you can achieve productivity improvements and increase the quality of work at your organization.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Part 1: Human Resource Management (HRM) Metric: Recruitment

The survey instrument used in getting research outputs about recruitment were made successfully into it. Both qualitative and quantitative interpretations and analysis were made to support the research study about HRM metric recruitment:

HRM Metric (Time to Fill)	Applicants	Employees
Time to Fill	Yes	No
Return on Investment (ROI)	No	Yes
Performance Productivity	No	Yes

Table 4. Research Survey results about HRM Metric (Time to Fill)

HRM Metric (Time to Fill)	Satisfied/ Always/ Agree	Not Satisfied/ Not Always/ Disagree	No Comment
Effectiveness	✓		
Usefulness		✓	
Efficiency		✓	
Accuracy	✓		
Knowledge	✓		

Table 5. HRM Metric results using Time to Fill

HRM Metric (Time to Hire)	Applicants	Employees
Time to Hire	Yes	No
Return on Investment (ROI)	Yes	Yes
Performance Productivity	No	Yes

Table 6. Research Survey results about HRM Metric (Time to Hire)

HRM Metric (Time to Hire)	Satisfied/ Always/ Agree	Not Satisfied/ Not Always/ Disagree	No Comment
Effectiveness	✓		
Usefulness	✓		
Efficiency	✓		
Accuracy	✓		
Knowledge	✓		

Table 7. HRM Metric results using Time to Hire

Part 2: Human Resource Management (HRM) Metric: Return on Investment (ROI)

$$\text{HCROI} = \frac{\text{Net Benefits} - \text{Cost}}{\text{Cost}}$$

Suppose the firm roll out a “Campus Job Fair” initiatives in the workplace, costing approximately Php 250,000 good for 10 days. Those are your human capital expenses. The savings for (reduction in stress, absenteeism, burnout, etc.) made this initiative amounts to Php 700,000. Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{HCROI} &= \text{Php } 700,000 - \text{Php } 250,000 / \text{Php } 250,000 \\ &= 2 \text{ (which is represented as a ratio 2:1)} \end{aligned}$$

This means that for every Php 1 you spent on the wellness program, there was a benefit of Php 2. There are variables you need to consider, of course, when analyzing things in this way (for example, the measurement period of the cost-saving).

Part 3: Human Resource Management (HRM) Metric: Employee Productivity

The results of the research survey regarding Employee Productivity index presented by Diliman College (DC), is to measure its Employees Performance Appraisal (EPA) among the employees of the said organization. For the motivation and dedication of the employees, its best for them to acquire and regulate EPA, intended for performance based resolutions and management productivity. To better understand EPA, there are guidelines and basis for the company to conduct EPA:

Performance Appraisal Interventions: Deterline, W.A. and Rosenberg, M.J. Eds., (1992). PMS is a great change tool. However most organization treat it merely as a system to manage people or as a human resource management system than as a

change management system. The potential of this tool has been grossly underestimated and attention paid to this and investments made on this are extremely small. The most important investment it requires is a managerial time. The even this time is a mere 1% to 5% of each manager's time in a year to plan, review, and develop the performance, competencies and culture of individuals, dyads, teams and the organization as a whole.

To fully understand the potentials of PMS:

First. Examine the multiple objectives of PMS and choose the objectives that are manageable in a short span and in the long run.

Second. Use a participative approach. Get top management commitment. Help them to experience how it helps them focus their work, plan time and maximize their impact. PMS facilitator should be knowledgeable in behavioral sciences. The person should be process sensitive, know goal setting, identify Key Performance Areas KPAs, difference between KPAs & KRAs (Key result Areas), force field analysis, coaching, biases in ratings etc.

Third. The interventions may include education program, training internal resource persons etc. A good PMS can create new culture of transparency, integrity, and promote OCTAPACE values mentioned earlier. The intervention should be system driven and should involve the whole system. It is as "the integrated use of training and development, organization development, and career development to improve individual, group, and organizational effectiveness."

Human Resource Management (HRM) Interventions:

The Human Resource Management (HRM) Intervention used by the said academic institution is greatly affecting their overall HR functions of the organization. These were set by the management and executives to look into the possible academic integrations and HRM progressions. Primarily, the HRM Interventions quantifies the human resource management processes and evaluations, to ensure the HRM guidelines and standards of hiring and firing employees are always met. This will also serve as their basis for HRM policies and company regulations. Amendments and changes on this HRM Interventions can still be part of their HRM discretions and management directives.

Employee Selection:

The Employee Assurance Selection (EAS) is by picking the ideal person to manage everything. The cycle begins with a definite depiction of the capacities as well as data, experiences, and individual characteristics expected to accomplish the work

endeavors. The Critical and the focal points for Human Resource Planning (HRD) and Human Resource Management (HRM) are made exclusively by capable people and individuals' view of talented performers. The assurance employee selection cycle contrasts in a multifaceted design among affiliated organizations and business partners. Some of these is to fill rightful positions quickly and monetarily by looking at the resumes and application reference structures. Various affiliations select likely delegates by multifaceted, and at times extravagant, assurance systems including position related tests, a movement of gatherings, and authentic checks. Decisions regarding the employee assurance selection are critical for convincing on various employment leveled executions.

Image 4: Human Resource Management (HRM) Interventions in an academic setting

Employees Compensation and Benefits:

The employees' compensation and benefits programs are related to cash which targeted compensation courses of action, that includes consolidated repayments, delegates' previous remunerations, employees monetary arrangement, and motivational benefits factors of employees. Every compensation and benefits programs are done by a pay for work execution, pay disputes, yielded pay, prosperity or incidental pay, pay to risk security, grievance pay, and the pay to spousal employees compensation when there is employment inclinations.

Motivation (Incentives and Rewards):

The motivation driving force interface pay with a standard employment execution are usually arranged in a full business intent for every rightful chosen employee. These can be short or a long incentive employment stretch, and can let the employees enjoy his or her employment tenureship. The monetary inspiring powers for additional remuneration, flexible differential pay, yielded pay, and various pre-requisites and employment considerations should be assessed and processed according to the Human Resource Management guidelines. Examples of this are: management incentives, that is considered participatory goal setting and decision making, and other career motivational opportunities.

Employment Performance Appraisals:

Employment Performance Appraisal (EPA) are also considered HRM assessments and evaluations. This to help individuals in managing their employment progression, and and to create a positive performance indications. The examples of this are various moterary benefits for a positive and affirming employment assessments, able to perform jobs effectively, and a clear progressive employment goals, and better a human resource orchestrating. It also suggests a that employees whether rank and file and supervisory employees to execute positive and progressive employment assessments so that performance appraisals kicks in. This may also effect on every employees performance productivity status and promotional aspirations. Proper evaluations and feedbacks are also an effective ways to measure each of the employees performance appraisals. For some, monthly perfect attendances, and an outstanding job status are given to deserving employees in the company.

Assessment Centers and Competency Training:

The employees' competency and training process is where the standardized employment assurance frameworks are applied into. It generally separates the management employees training evaluations from the rank and file employees. Every employees must be trained and evaluated whether they are prepared and competent on performing their destined capacities. Others see it as a retraining and retooling each employees where HR executives usually evaluates, give notice, record, and survey how employees comply with any working conditions in the company. Training manuals, and modules talks about employees performance welfare, account specifications and employment practices where employees should know about.

Competency Planning and Career Pathing:

Competency Planning and Career Pathing is a purposeful distinctive employment evidence where employees aspires for a corporate senior positions. It entails long term employment stretch by organizing developmental management roles. Also, it means competency planning and a career pathing development that is to contribute leadership undertakings to qualified and aspiring academic head, faculty office supervisor, and other academic managers upward career development. And to integrate better organizational career pathing and

Management and Supervisory Development:

Employees from the management and supervisory positions that involves on improvement and development is the Human Resource Management (HRM) policy guidance, planning, knowledge transfer, management skills demonstrations as managers and supervisors by their respective organizations. It is also connected to an adjusting workplace by means complexity, strong and manageable organization that maintains the corporate primary objective, framework, goals, targets, and market position. An authoritative progression made by supervisors and managers are expected to work at professional means and be responsibly meeting the objectives of an association and the necessities of its laborers. The driving force of supervisors and managers are also measure on its leadership skills, competence and management

authority.

Retirement Planning:

To have positive experiences in retirement, people ought to plan. At absolutely no point in the future is retirement looked at as withdrawal, retreat, and confinement, and retirement Planning. To have positive experiences in retirement planning, employees of a certain firm must always plan ahead. Better Retirement Planning will never be looked as an employment withdrawal, retreat, and employees solitude. The current labor guidelines suggests that new words for retirement planning will be the employees' reorientation, recommitment, reinvention, reinvolved, regeneration, renewal, renovation, redirection, reinvestigation, replenishment, and reexploration. Retirement planning is usually part of a benefits employment package. A retired employee should know also and be aware about finding their retirement planning arrangements, and personal life satisfaction.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Only rightful and qualified candidate to any job positions are usually chosen by different companies according from their Human Resource Management (HRM) proposals they get into. So it means, a potential applicant should know the valuable aspect of recruitment and selection process. Wherein the Recruitment process are done in a fast paced HRM evaluations, while the Selection process requires a lot of HR and management assessments and approvals. But several HRM metric/s can be done to make these human resource management process for an organization be easier and effective for them. And to make an organization be an HR manageable and successful, here are some of the human resource management (HRM) recommendations to follow:

1.) **Hire the Right Workers:** The business have to show how they're utilizing the right employees in a single company, and who can join them by means of their standard recruitment process. If the business operations have a social occasion of employees who are valuable and can oversee everything, the company had to resolve issues and challenges right away for involving candidates' personal traits and work inclinations.

2.) **Show the applicants how they're very important:** This is to make sure that every qualified candidate on a given job vacancy are very important and how critical they are in terms of employment selection. Occasionally, the recruitment selection really works on both clerical and supervisory positions. During this stage, applicants should know how to appreciate, give time, and value every application they have in one company. Because at the end the day, the rightful owners of the firm will have to make their own decisions and employment arrangements for the chosen and successful newbie selected.

3.) **Listen to Applicants Feedback:** Always give your applicants a chance to give considerations or suggestion analysis. Make an effort to listen and have pardon on

some feedbacks made by applicants, so that company will make its recruitment adjustments. Then, reclassify every recruitment and selection process on each levels of job titles, and have an enough time to adjust and follow company guidelines on the employment selection of employees.

4.) Invest in Human Resource Planning: Once the company decided that they are ready to initiate recruitment, selection, employment evaluations, and other human resource management processes, the organization have to remember that offering jobs to qualified applicants should be plan first, assessed possible human resource metrics, and invest in human resource planning. The benefits and effects of a human resource planning, like job advertisements, applicant's evaluation processes and other related human resource expenses are very important to reduced unwanted HRM conflicts and problems for them to value business investments and profits.

As we shortlisted and considered newly hired employees to our businesses, please remember that the HRM metrics mentioned above are very effective and can be use in a logical and measureable circumstances. But of course, the management and the HRM discretions and decisions are still the ultimate power to consider on hiring and firing employees within. So in other words, know the person first based on his/her personal traits and character (attitude and behavior) and quantify them based on their work experiences and capabilities to work (competencies).

REFERENCES

- Aghion, P., Howitt, P. (1994). Growth and unemployment. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 61(3), 477–494.
- Balliester, Thereza and Adam Elsheikhi. (2018). *The Future of Work: A Literature Review*. ILOResearch Department Working Paper No. 29. International Labour Office. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---inst/documents/publication/wcms_625866.pdf (Date accessed: April 15, 2019)
- Brenchley, Christopher (2019). *The Hidden Cost of Hiring. Time for a New Alternative. Surehand, Inc.* 17500 Depot St., Suite 170, Morgan Hill, CA, 95037.
- Cost-Per-Hire: American National Standard (2012). *American National Standards Institute, Inc.* The Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM). 1800 Duke Street, Alexandria, VA 22314 or to HRSTDS@SHRM.ORG.
- Deterline, W.A. and Rosenberg, M.J. Eds., (1992). *Workplace productivity: Performance technology success stories*. Washington, D.C.: NSPI, pp. 5-6. Used with permission of the International Society for Performance Improvement .

- Goldin, C., Katz, L.F., 2009. *The Race Between Education and Technology*. Harvard University Press.
- Government of the Philippines, Department of Education. (2020). *Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 in Light of the Covid-19 Public Health Emergency*. Pasig City.
- Government of the Philippines, Department of Education. (2019). *Classroom Observation Tool*. Pasig City.
- Government of the Philippines, Department of Education. (2019). *Results-based Performance Management System Updated Manual*. Pasig City.
- Government of the Philippines, Department of Education. (2017). *National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers*. Pasig City.
- Government of the Philippines, Department of Education. (2016). *The Learning Action Cell as a K to 12 Basic Education Program School-based Continuing Professional Development Strategy for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning*. Pasig City.
- Government of the Philippines, Department of Education. (2016). *Policy Guidelines on Daily Lesson Preparation for the K to 12 Basic Education Program*. Pasig City.
- Government of the Philippines, Department of Education. (2015). *Guidelines on the Enhanced School Improvement Planning (SIP) Process and the School Report Card (SRC)*.
- Government of the Philippines, Department of Education – CALABARZON. (2019). *PIVOT 4A Budget of Work in All Learning Areas in Key Stage 1-4 (version 2.0)*. Cainta.
- Government of the Philippines, Department of Education (2019)- Undersecretary for Curriculum and Instruction. 2020. *Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of Learning Delivery Modalities for the Formal Education*. Pasig City.
- Government of the Philippines, Department of Education – Teacher Education Council. (2019). *Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) Resource Package Module 17*. Pasig City
- Higgins, J., Cooperstein, G., Peterson, M. (2011). *HR Analytics as a Strategic Workforce Planning*

- Joly, E., & Venturiello, M. (2012). Persons with Disabilities: Entitled to Beg, not to Work. *The Argentine Case*, 39(3), 325-347. doi: 10.1177/0896920512446758
- Lancu, S. (2022). What is Time to Fill? Everything You Need to Know About This Recruiting Metric. *Academy to Innovate HR (AIHR)*. <https://www.aihr.com/blog/what-is-time-to-fill/>
- Momin, W.Y.M., & Mishra, K. (2015). HR Analytics as a Strategic Workforce Planning. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(4), 258-260.
- Ulrich, D. (1997). Measuring Human Resources: An overview of practice and a prescription for results. Attitude as it relates to Training and Work Proficiency. *Sage Open*, 1-13, <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/2158244011433338>.
- Understanding the Return on Investment from TVET: A Practical Guide, (2020). *United Nations and Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization UNESCO, and National Centre for Vocational Education Research (NCVER)*.
- Unilab Foundation (2016). Project Inclusion. Retrieved from <http://www.unilabfoundation.org/ULFWeb/6/program/project-inclusion>
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (1999). Programme for the *Education of Children in Difficult Circumstances: street children, working children...access to education, even for the most destitute*. https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000118101_eng?posInS&t=1&queryId=9046c1d9-f537-4e9c-9641-9d4d93b0a429
- University of Tasmania. (2020). *Constructive Feedback Principles*. <https://www.utas.edu.au/curriculum-and-quality/student-surveys/evaluate/constructive-feedback-principles> - :~:text=Constructive%20feedback%20is%20providing%20useful,feedback%20is%20a%20valuable%20skill
- Vulpen, E.V. (2022). How to Calculate Productivity: An HR's Guide. *Academy to Innovate HR (AIHR)*. <https://www.aihr.com/blog/how-to-calculate-productivity/>
- Vulpen, E.V. (2022). Human Capital ROI: Definition, Formula, and Calculation. *Academy to Innovate HR (AIHR)*. <https://www.aihr.com/blog/human-capital-roi/>
- Vulpen, E.V. (2022). 14 HR Metric Examples. *Academy to Innovate HR (AIHR)*. <https://www.aihr.com/blog/14-hr-metrics-examples/>